

Environmental Data Science Innovation & Inclusion Lab

Year 3 Social Network Analysis

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Executive Summary

Network characteristics

 The network analysis identified **over 500 people and 250 organizations** that make up a portion of the ESIL network.

 Members of the ESIL network (defined as people who have attended at least one ESIL event) **have increased** from Year 1 (n=202) to Year 3 (n=667) by 230%

 Connectedness among members of the ESIL network has increased by over 60% as indicated by the increased average degree centrality values from Year 1 to Year 3.

 Members of the ESIL leadership team are the **most centralized** to the network and can disseminate information across the network effectively. However, **more people outside of the leadership team** are becoming central to the network by acting as bridges to different areas of the network as evidenced by their high values of betweenness centrality.

 NEON (National Ecological Observatory Network) and **Boulder-based organizations** (CU, EarthLab, CIRES) continue to be the **most central organizations** in the ESIL network. One **tribal college** is also included in the top 10 most connected organizations.

 The **Environmental Data Science (EDS) roles and research connections** continue to be the largest and most prevalent dimensions of the ESIL network.

 Connections across all categories of collaboration are **well-developed** throughout the network, particularly around the ESIL leadership team.

 Advocates for communities underrepresented in EDS and members of communities underrepresented in EDS are a **small but well-connected dimension** of the ESIL network as evidenced by the relatively high average degree centrality. Students, however, are the **least connected** among the ESIL member roles.

Suggestions for Use of Network Data

- Collaborations among students could be **areas of focus for connection building** across people and organizations in the network.
- Identify central people outside of the leadership team to **help build connectivity** within the network as they bridge collaborators at the periphery of the network with the more well-connected areas adjacent to the leadership team.
- In addition to reporting the number of people and organizations represented in the network maps to show **growth in network size**, also use average degree centrality as a key metric for **growth in connectivity** among network members and organizations.

*"Collaboration" by Eko Purnomo, "Network" by Desi Aulia, "Network" by Ikonicon, "Organization" by Soremba, "Research" by Eucalyp, "Communication" by Creative Stall pk, "connected" by Travis Avery, "summit" by Kemesah Maharjan np all from the [Noun Project](#).

Introduction

The Environmental Data Science Innovation and Inclusion Lab (ESIL) evaluation team uses social network analysis (SNA) to characterize ESIL's network each year and to evaluate changes to the network since its start (see evaluation question right). The evaluation team analyzes both the entire ESIL network (e.g. people and organizations) and ESIL members' personal networks to gather information about who engages with ESIL and how ESIL members interact with others.

Baseline network information was collected in Year 1 at the inaugural ESIL Innovation summit (2023). The Innovation Summit provided a great opportunity to evaluate the ESIL network because it brought together ESIL leadership and existing partners within the environmental data science community while also intentionally invited other EDS leaders and EDS professionals and future ESIL community members to build an inclusive community committed to open science, diverse teams and community-driven approaches to data science. Thus, the participants in the first year Innovation Summit were defined as the ESIL network.

Since Year 1, changes have been made to the SNA data collection: 1) Network surveys are no longer tied to Innovation Summit participation, 2) Network surveys are sent out to ESIL members twice a year, and 3) ESIL network members are defined as people who have participated in at least one ESIL event. Implementation of these changes has allowed the evaluation team to recruit from ESIL members more broadly and provide members with more opportunities to share about their personal and organizational networks in EDS. Furthermore, it allows for more accurate comparisons from year to year now that the ESIL network is clearly defined (e.g. closed network).

This Year 3 Social Network Analysis Report characterizes the people and organizations within the ESIL network. The report presents cumulative data from three waves of network surveys to characterize the ESIL network now and discusses changes from Year 1 to Year 3 in terms of network size and connectedness. The report will also offer recommendations on how the network data could be used for communication across ESIL and connection building.

How has ESIL grown the environmental data science community and expanded its connections (e.g., through building connections between fields and existing networks and bringing in new people and organizations)?

Methods

Updated Recruitment and Survey Design

Identifying Network Members

The evaluation team coordinated with ESIL’s community engagement specialist who keeps track of ESIL event participation to identify network members (e.g. members who had attended at least 1 ESIL event). At the time of the most recent survey, there were 667 ESIL network members. Those members who had completed a network survey before were emailed the list of collaborators (both people and organizations) they identified in the previous survey(s) for reference and asked to complete the network survey again to update their connections. First time survey takers were provided with a general invite and link to the survey.

Survey Updates

The standalone network survey asked members to describe their role in EDS and what ESIL events they had previously participated in. The list of roles included one new option – Community engagement and/or Outreach professional – based on the “other” responses we received in the baseline network survey. The survey kept the categorization of EDS-specific and non-EDS specific roles and subsequent questions related to their connections and the nature of those collaborations.

Additional collaboration types were added for survey respondents (again, based on the “other” options written in by previous respondents). The new collaboration types recognize collaborative work in professional societies, academic and work-related relationships and participation in non-research events and programs (see right).

Please indicate the nature of your collaboration with (Select all that apply.)*

- Ongoing research
- Grant proposals for future research
- Co-author on papers
- Collaboration on data products
- Collaboration on code or software tools
- Collaboration on educational materials
- Preliminary discussions/potential collaborator
- Learning
- Participate with in presentations, panels, programs and/or communities of practice
- Communicate with as leader/member of the same professional organization/working group
- Mentor, advisor/advisee, and/or host institution relationship
- Co-worker, employer, or other work relationship
- Other (please explain)

Data Cleaning and Analysis

Data were collected using Qualtrics and were analyzed using both quantitative and qualitative approaches. All social network analysis was completed in the online social network analysis program [Kumu](#), an online platform for mapping networks and systems. Kumu outputs 12 metrics for SNA to

highlight individuals and organizations within a network based on their connections (e.g., degree, closeness, and betweenness).

Open-ended responses to the “nature of collaboration” questions were coded manually in Microsoft Excel by labeling them as one or more of the broad categories (Research, Resources, Interpersonal Communications). The codes were decided based on a response’s similarity or agreement to any of the response options within each category. The most common open-ended responses included Research collaborations (such as presenting on panels or having an advisor/advisee relationship), Interpersonal Communications collaborations (such as knowing another individual as an organization’s representative or from a shared working group), and Professional Community collaborations (such as being co-workers with another individual).

Once responses were qualitatively coded, the data spreadsheet was cleaned and restructured using R version 4.4.0, in preparation for upload to the SNA program Kumu. Data cleaning entailed merging and formatting the 3 waves of data ; identifying spelling mistakes or duplicate responses with different spellings and modifying them to a corrected and unique spelling; and assigning sub-categories of responses to the four broader categories (e.g. assigning survey option 1 - Ongoing Research to the category Research).

After cleaning, the data was restructured into a list of connections (detailing the two people connected, the direction of the connection, and the categories the nature of collaboration falls under) and a list of nodes (detailing the ID and corresponding information for each person and organization in the network). The two lists were used as inputs in Kumu to create the network maps.

Network Maps

The social network maps below cumulative data from over the past three waves of data collection (from 2023 to 2025) and represent the current state of the ESIL network. Nearly 300 network members have responded to at least one network survey – and for those who have responded to multiple survey waves, their most recent responses are in the network maps below. The maps represent 44% of the ESIL network population (667 people as of Jan 2025).

In the maps, the circles are called “nodes,” representing individual people and/or organizations who took the survey and/or were named as collaborators. The lines in between the circles represent a “tie” or “connection” between the nodes, in this case when a survey respondent mentioned that they collaborated with a specific person or organization. For these maps, ties do not have a direction; instead, if one person identified a collaboration with another, then we considered the collaboration as reciprocated. The position of the nodes in each map is in a circular format for ease of visual comparison of connections between the whole network maps and maps of network dimensions.

Each node position can be manipulated in kumu to more easily visualize areas of connection density and identify “bridges” - people or organizations that tie two different groups of the network together.

Individual nodes (i.e. isolates) - people who took the survey but did not identify any connections - and small unconnected groups within the network (constellations) are also useful data points in the network analysis.

The characteristics of the network (and changes to network characteristics) can be measured with indicators such as network size (of nodes and connections), density and the average degree centrality of network members. The evaluation team has identified average degree centrality and density metrics to quantify network connectivity within the ESIL network and across network dimensions (e.g. EDS roles and collaboration types) to indicate growth in connections between people and organizations of the network over time.

(Note: Numbers are used to identify people and organizations. Due to IRB protocol, the identity of individual people is protected through the use of an unidentifiable number in the maps. A list of all organizations depicted in the networks and their corresponding identification number is included in the Appendix.)

ESiIL Network Maps

People and Organizations within the ESiIL Network

Figure 1: Network map of the ESiIL network including both people (blue nodes; n=316) and organizations (yellow nodes; n=261). **Thicker lines connecting nodes indicate more developed collaborations.** Yellow rectangle shows area depicted in Figure 1a.

The whole network map (Fig. 1) represents all respondents to any network survey (n=295) and as well as all the people (n=316) and organizations (n=261) the respondents identified as connections. The whole network map provides a snapshot of the ESiIL network as of January 2025. Lines between nodes show where connections exist between people and/or organizations and the thickness of the line

represents the different types of connections that are present between nodes. The nature of the connection categories can be grouped according to connections made through research, resources, and interpersonal communication. The thicker lines represent connections that span more than one of these connection categories. The thickest lines between nodes indicate that the connections are defined by all three nature of the connection categories and thus are considered multi-faceted (and potentially more developed) connection types.

Figure 1a: Enlarged area of Figure 1 to show the details of the personal and organizational connections.

In the enlarged area of the whole network map, the connections among people and organizations can be seen more clearly. Each person and organization are labeled with a numerical identifier. In this area of the network, note that person 51 has one connection with person 122 (blue node) and connections with two organizations (yellow nodes). The nature of person 51's connections with person 122 and the organizations span research, resource, communication categories (thickest lines, ex: 51-533). Other connections (such as the one between person 134 and organization 464) are more focused within one nature of collaboration category. The personal and organizational network of 122 is connected to other personal and organizational networks within ESIL. Person 122's relationship with Person 51 indirectly connects the former to other organizations within the ESIL network (ex: 441 and 533) and vice versa (ex: Person 51 to 571, 605, and 510). This offers just one example of how people are connected within the ESIL network and the sum of these direct and indirect connections produce the web of the ESIL network depicted in Figure 1.

People in the ESIL Network

Figure 2: Map of personal connections within the ESIL network. The nodes (n=316) represent people who are members of the ESIL network. **Larger nodes have more connections and thicker connecting lines indicate developed connections (e.g. include different types of collaboration).**

Relationships among the members of the ESIL network are presented in Figure 2. The network surveys ask people to name up to 20 collaborators with whom they work on EDS. This map only depicts the connections among members of the ESIL network including the people who responded to the surveys (n=268) and people they named as connections who did not respond to the surveys. The size of the node reflects the degree centrality for that person, meaning that larger nodes represent people with more connections relative to others. In this map, the thickness of the line between nodes represents the number of connection categories that describe the nature of the collaboration (e.g., research, resource, and interpersonal communication).

Whole network statistics for ESIL

Overall, the network statistics for the people and organizations of the ESIL network broadly characterize the network (Table 1). The social network analysis measures included are:

- 1) number of nodes, the total number of people or organizations in the network;
- 2) number of connections, the total number of reported connections between people/organizations in the network;
- 3) average degree, the average number of connections per person/organization; and
- 4) density, the number of connections as a proportion to the number of connections possible.

Table 1. Whole ESIL network statistics

	# Nodes	# Connections	Average Degree	Density
People and Organizations	602	1128	3.75	0.006
People	316	537	3.4	0.011

The number of nodes and connections within the two sub-networks (e.g. people and organizations vs. people-only) are used to calculate the density of each of the sub-networks. The people network is slightly denser than the network of people and organizations but both networks have relatively low density values given that the networks both have isolates (e.g. nodes without any connections). When considering both the people and organizations in the ESIL network, the average number of connections per node (e.g. average degree centrality) is higher than the people network alone (On average, 3.75 connections per node vs. 3.4 connections per node respectively).

Furthermore, these metrics quantify how the ESIL network is changing over time (e.g. compare growth, level of connectivity, etc.). We hypothesized that the number of nodes and connections in the ESIL network would grow each year, and that we'd see higher average degree centrality and network density values as relationships among people and organizations within ESIL develop over time. However, density values are typically lower in large networks than in smaller networks because it is difficult for the number of connections a person or organization has to keep pace with the number of available connections in a large network (Borgatti et al., 2018). Thus, because the size of the network in Year 1 is much smaller than the network in Year 3, average degree is a better measure for comparison (See Table 2). **Since Year 1, the average degree of the people and organizations in the ESIL network has increased 60% or more, indicating that nodes within the network are creating more connections to others.**

Table 2. Comparison of network stats from Year 1 to Year 3

	Yr 1 Average Degree	Yr 1 Density	Yr 3 Average Degree	Yr 3 Density	% Change
People and Organizations	2.35	0.008	3.75	0.006	+60% AD -25% Density
People	2.02	0.017	3.4	0.011	+68% AD -35% Density

Personal network statistics for ESIL

Centrality measures

Table 3 lists the top ten nodes representing people and organizations with the highest centrality within the ESIL network. Common social network analysis centrality measures include:

- 1) Degree centrality (the measure of the number of connections for a node),
- 2) Closeness centrality (the normalized distance* each node is from all other nodes in the network), and
- 3) Betweenness centrality (the number of times a node falls along the shortest path between two other nodes) (Borgatti et al, 2018).

Each centrality measure provides different information for each node. Degree centrality helps to understand the structural importance of individual nodes within the network (Borgatti et al. 2018). In general, nodes with high degree centrality are the local connectors/hubs within the network but are not necessarily the best connected across the wider network. Nodes with high closeness can spread information to the rest of the network most easily and usually have high visibility into what is happening across the network because of their proximity to other nodes within the network. Nodes with high betweenness centrality have more control over the flow of information and act as bridges within the network (or potential points of failure) because of their position between nodes. **The distance is calculated by counting the number of connections composing the shortest path between nodes and then normalized by dividing that value (n) into n-1.*

In terms of degree centrality, all but two of the ten nodes are associated with the ESIL leadership team with the top two people having over 40 connections each (either that they identified themselves or that were identified by others who completed the survey). Organizations are listed as well with NEON (National Ecological Observatory Network), ESIL, University of Colorado Boulder, and EarthLab holding the top four spots. Figure 3 visually represents the degree centrality among the top people (blue squares) and organizations (yellow squares) within the network. The figure depicts the nodes with more than 30 connections, which is equal to 4 people and one organization (NEON) within the network. This representation demonstrates the ability of the leadership team to connect members of the network and the importance that the leadership team plays in spreading information to the rest of the network.

Table 3: Top 10 people and 10 organizations with the greatest number of connections, closeness and betweenness centrality. People outside of the ESIL leadership in *orange italics* font.

	Node ID	Degree Centrality	Node ID	Closeness Centrality	Node ID	Betweenness Centrality
#1	313	43	411	0.308	411	0.089
#2	411	40	313	0.306	313	0.061
#3	194	36	186	0.302	413	0.057
#4	186	31	194	0.294	<i>351</i>	0.055
#5	413	27	91	0.289	<i>275</i>	0.055
#6	91	27	413	0.286	186	0.054
#7	93	22	93	0.273	<i>237</i>	0.046
#8	<i>58</i>	22	204	0.272	91	0.033
#9	204	22	177	0.27	194	0.033
#10	<i>7</i>	19	<i>7</i>	0.268	<i>369</i>	0.024

	Org Name	Degree Centrality	Org Name	Closeness Centrality	Org Name	Betweenness Centrality
#1	NEON	43	NEON	0.308	NEON	0.089
#2	ESIL	40	ESIL	0.306	NOAA	0.061
#3	CU Boulder	36	CU Boulder	0.302	ESIL	0.057
#4	EarthLab	31	EarthLab	0.294	UW Madison	0.055
#5	LTER	27	USGS	0.289	NASA	0.055
#6	NCEAS	27	LTER	0.286	NCEAS	0.054
#7	USGS	22	Univ of Arizona	0.273	LTER	0.046
#8	Oglala Lakota College	22	NCEAS	0.272	USGS	0.033
#9	NOAA	22	ESIP	0.27	CU Boulder	0.033
#10	CIRES	19	CIRES	0.268	NEON	0.024

Figure 3: Nodes with the greatest degree centrality in the ESiIL network and their direct connections (4 people and 1 organization). Blue squares represent people and yellow squares represent organizations with **high degree centrality (>30 degrees)** within the network.

In terms of closeness centrality, again, all but one (**bold**) are members of the ESiIL leadership team. NEON, ESiIL, University of Colorado Boulder, and EarthLab continue to hold the top four places in the

list. There is more diversity in terms of who are the important bridges of information within the ESIL network (e.g. Betweenness Centrality). Three of the top ten nodes with high betweenness centrality are members of the ESIL leadership team, and the NEON, NOAA, ESIL and University of Wisconsin Madison are seen to be key bridges as well. Four of the ten top nodes of betweenness are people outside of the research team. These centrality measures characterize how individual nodes fit within the larger network and it makes sense that those with high centrality are within the leadership team and associated with organizations with strong ties to the ESIL leaders. Over time and growth of ESIL, we hypothesize that centrality measures should increase for people and organizations across a larger portion of the network.

Network Dimensions

Personal Role

ESIL summit participants self-identified what role(s) they have within the broad field of Environmental Data Science (EDS). The roles fall into two groups: roles that are EDS-specific and roles that are not EDS-specific (which include advocates and members from communities underrepresented in EDS and students). We can view these role categories as network dimensions and compare them to one another with respect to their size and density. For comparison, Figures 4-7 represent social network maps of the people with EDS-specific roles, non-EDS specific roles, those engaged with/representatives of communities underrepresented within EDS, and students. In these maps, survey respondents and their connections are depicted. Thicker lines connecting nodes indicate a greater number of connection types (e.g. span different categories of connection nature) and/or multiple connections within a single connection category.

Table 3. Roles within the field of Environmental Data Science with number of people selecting those roles (n).

EDS-specific roles (n=172)	Non-EDS-specific roles (n=83)
People working in Environmental, Biological, Social Science field (n=139)	Advocate for underrepresented communities, including Tribal nations (n=34)
People working in Computational and/or Data Science field (n=77)	Member of (underrepresented) community, including Tribal nations (n=30)
Data provider (n=36)	Community engagement and/or Outreach professional (n=5)
(Data science) Educator (n=51)	Student (n=38)
Application partner (n=8)	Other (n=7)
Industry representative (n=3)	
Synthesis center member (n=28)	
Artificial Intelligence, Machine Learning and Analytics professional (n=28)	

Figure 4: Map of network members with EDS-specific roles. The blue nodes represent people who completed the survey and their named collaborators within the network. **Over half of the 316 people comprising the network identify as working in EDS-specific roles.** In general, connections within the EDS-specific role dimension of the network are numerous among nodes representing the ESIL leadership team and represent more than one connection category. The well-connected nodes also reach people outside of the leadership team, but isolates remain toward the edges of the network map.

Figure 5: Map of network members that are in non-EDS-specific roles: The blue nodes represent people who completed the survey and their named collaborators within the network. **Less than a third of the 316 people comprising the network identify as working in non-EDS-specific roles.** Similar to Figure 4, connections within this dimension of the network are numerous among the nodes representing the ESIL leadership team and represent more than one connection category. However, the well-connected nodes do not reach as many people outside of the leadership team, nor are people outside of the leadership team well-connected to one another.

Figure 6: Map of people who advocate for or describe that they come from communities underrepresented in EDS. This map dimension shows a similar pattern to that of Figure 5, connections within this dimension of the network are numerous among the nodes representing the ESIL leadership team and represent more than one connection category. The well-connected nodes do not reach as many people outside of the leadership team, and there are fewer isolated nodes in the map.

Figure 7: Map of student population. The student nodes are isolated from one another and have few connections revealing limited connectivity across the network.

Overall the network of people in EDS-specific roles are more numerous and have more connections than those in non-EDS-specific roles in the entire ESiIL network. In the maps of both dimensions, connections are more numerous between people who are central to the network (e.g. ESiIL leadership) but also connect nodes more broadly across the network (more-so in the EDS-specific map dimension). Connections range from more unidimensional (thin lines of connection, connected only by a single activity) to more developed (thick lines of connection, connected by a range of activities). The maps

depicting the advocates for/members of communities underrepresented in EDS dimension show more limited reach across the network, again tied more closely to ESIL leadership members than to the entire network. Where connections exist between members within these communities, they appear to be more developed (e.g. thick connection lines) both with people more central the network and/or within their isolated constellations of connections (See Network Statistics). The student network is the least connected to one another among ESIL dimensions.

Types of Collaboration

ESIL summit participants were asked to define the nature of their connections to other people by selecting from a list of 13 different types of collaboration that were identified by the ESIL leadership team. The nature of the connections falls into three groups (see below) and can be viewed as additional network dimensions to compare to one another and to the dimensions by role in terms of their size and density. The “other” category allowed participants to describe the nature of their connection and these answers were binned into one of the broad categories below.

Table 4. Categories for different types of connections with the number of people with those connection types (n).

Research Connections (n=310)	Resource Connections (n=203)	Interpersonal Connections (n=289)
Ongoing research	Collaboration on data products	Preliminary discussions
Grant proposals for future research	Collaboration on code or software tools	Learning
Co-author on papers	Collaboration on educational materials	Communicate with as leader/member of the same professional organization/working group
Participate with in presentations, panels, programs and/or communities of practice		Co-worker, employer, or other work relationship
Mentor, advisor/advisee, and/or host institution relationship		

The following maps display these dimensions of the larger ESIL network as it relates to the nature of the connections that people have with one another (Figures 8-11). In these maps, all people (both survey respondents and named collaborators) are depicted in each dimension. Connections among survey respondents and their named collaborators are displayed according to connection category and connection thickness represents the number of connections between nodes.

Figure 8: Map of Research Connections. People who completed the survey are represented by the dark blue color and those that did not complete the survey are in white. This map showcases the research connections only. **Research connections are the most prevalent type of connection that survey respondents selected to describe the nature of their connection to others in their personal networks.** Research connections span across the network map and include a number of people who did not complete the survey but are ESiIL members.

Figure 9: Map of Resource Connections. People who completed the survey are represented by the dark blue color and those that did not complete the survey are in white. This map showcases the resource connections only. **Fewer people identified connections that are related to collaboration on resources** (software, code, educational materials, etc.) than those with research connections. Resource connections are **more concentrated** in the upper quadrant of the map near nodes of high centrality (See Fig. 2) but also include **smaller constellations of connections** throughout the network map.

Figure 10: Map of Interpersonal Communication Connections. People who completed the survey are represented by the dark blue color and those that did not complete the survey are white. This map showcases interpersonal communication connections only. **People identified numerous connections related to interpersonal communication whether it be through preliminary discussion on a project or idea or through contacting potential collaborators.** These connections are denser in the upper quadrant of the map near the nodes with high centrality, however, these types of connections also span across different zones of the network, albeit with less frequency than the research connections seen in Fig. 8.

Network statistics

Overall network trends across dimensions for all ESIL community members

Table 5. SNA measures of the network across dimensions of the ESIL’s personal networks

	# Nodes	# Connections	Average Degree	Density
People in EDS-specific roles	172	305	3.55	0.02
People in Non-EDS-specific roles	83	106	2.55	0.03
People who advocate for/are from groups underrepresented in EDS	49	78	3.18	0.07
Students	38	4	0.21	0.01
People with research connections	176	310	3.52	0.02
People with resource connections	132	203	3.08	0.02
People in communication with others	168	289	3.44	0.02

When comparing networks for the four role dimensions to each other, the networks for people in EDS-specific roles are by far the largest (172 nodes), followed by the non-EDS specific roles, advocates and people underrepresented in EDS, and student role dimensions. The most developed (e.g. connected) dimension network is that for the people in EDS-specific roles which has an average of 3.55 connections among people in its network; whereas people who advocate for/are from underrepresented groups in EDS and non-EDS-specific role dimensions networks have only an average of 3.18 connections and 2.55 connections respectively. The student role dimension is the least developed at 0.21 connections on average (see Average Degree measure in Table 5). Network density is greatest among advocates for/underrepresented groups in EDS, followed by people in non-EDS-specific roles, people in EDS-specific roles, and students. Taken together (average degree and density metrics), there is greater collaboration among people within the advocates for/underrepresented group role dimensions than for the other dimensions even though it is one of the smaller networks. **Comparing the average degree values from 2023 to 2025, we see an increase in the average degree value of the EDS-specific role dimension** but decreased connectivity within the other role dimensions (See Table 6).

When comparing dimensions by connection type, the research dimension is the most common connection of ESIL members, followed by the resource, and then communications (see Table 5). The research and communications dimension networks are relatively similar in terms of their connectivity (3.52 and 3.44 average degree). **Comparing the 2023 and 2025 average degree values for people with**

different types of connections, we see that there is increased connectivity for people with research (up 45%) and resource (up 31%) connections. We are not able to compare average degree values for people with interpersonal communications connections because of the difference in the way that the network surveys collected those data (e.g. different response options available to survey takers in 2023 than in 2025).

Table 6. Changes across dimensions of the ESIL’s personal networks

	Yr 1 Average Degree	Yr 3 Average Degree	% Change
People in EDS-specific roles	2.65	3.55	+34%
People in Non-EDS-specific roles	2.76	2.55	-8%
People who advocate for/are from groups underrepresented in EDS	3.26	3.18	-2%
Students	1.71	0.21	-88%
People with research connections	2.42	3.52	+45%
People with resource connections	2.36	3.08	+31%

Interpretations

The network survey questions embedded in the ESIL Innovation Summit survey gathered important social network data to **help characterize the people and organizations that are the basis for the ESIL network in Year 1**. In addition to determining the size of the whole network (people and organizations) and quantifying connections among nodes in the network, social network analysis allows for visualizing the network and the patterns of organization among different dimensions within the larger network. Centrality metrics describe how each node fits within the larger network and network density is an indicator for how connected the nodes are within the network, a good proxy for collaboration among people and organizations. Subsequent data collection in Years 2 and 3 allows us to network metrics across years and make interpretations about network growth among different network dimensions (e.g. roles, types of collaboration, etc.)

Overall, the number of people and organizations comprising the ESIL network is over 600 (300+ people and 300+ organizations). These maps represent data collected from 44% of the network members who responded to the network survey. The survey was sent to 667 ESIL network members (as of Jan 2025). Average degree centrality values (of connections each node has) are reliable metrics

for comparison of network growth over time. **Since Year 1, the average degree centrality values have increased by over 60% for organizations and people in the network and for the network members alone.** This indicates that there is greater connectivity among the organizations and people represented in the network maps and indicates that **ESiIL is serving as a place for people and organizations to make new connections with one another.**

As with the Year 1, the centrality measures for people and organizations indicated the importance of the people and organizations comprising the ESiIL leadership team. It makes sense that members of the ESiIL leadership team have the largest number of connections per node (e.g. degree centrality) and act as hubs connecting smaller network communities and as information spreaders to others in the network. The ESiIL leadership is highly visible to the rest of the network given their proximity to other nodes (e.g. closeness centrality). In comparison to Year 1, **there are more ESiIL network members with high values of betweenness centrality that are not members of the ESiIL leadership team.** This can be viewed as a measure of network growth in that the flow of information is not solely reliant upon the ESiIL leadership and that other network members have become more central to act as bridges to other people and organizations within the network.

Similar to Year 1, NEON plays a central role in connecting people within the ESiIL network. Currently, NEON has the highest values of centrality across all three centrality measures. In comparison to Year 1, **NEON's centrality values have increased across the board indicating that it has become an even more central organization to the ESiIL network over time.** Other central organizations include ESiIL, CU, EarthLab, and CIRES (Boulder-based organizations) and Ogalala Lakota College (Tribal College). As the ESiIL network matures, the network will likely have other people and organizations beyond the ESiIL leadership rise to the top 10 or even the top 20 in centrality metrics. This broadening of key contributors will be important for the sustainability of the network and to reach a broader audience for Environmental Data Science.

Analysis of the network dimensions according to personal role and connection type indicates that **EDS-specific roles and research connections continue to be the most predominant dimensions of the ESiIL network.** There continue to be more people who identify with EDS-specific roles than non-EDS-specific roles in the ESiIL network and **the average degree centrality for people in EDS-specific roles has increased since Year 1 while it has decreased for others in non-EDS specific roles.** Network dimensions such as advocates for groups underrepresented in EDS and those who identify as a member of a group underrepresented in EDS are small but not as connected as in years prior. Connectedness within this dimension is an important measure of inclusion as the network increases the diversity of participants and organizations. Research, resource and interpersonal communication collaborations appear throughout the network. **People with research and resource connections have shown an increase in their average degree centrality since Year 1, indicating that people are making new connections within ESiIL.** Analysis of the dimensions highlights the areas for the most growth within the network by focusing attention on developing greater connectivity among nodes, particularly among students in the network.

Assumptions, Limitations, and Next Steps

The social network analysis provides a snapshot of the larger ESIL network and its growth trends over time. As in previous reports, we assume that the survey respondents are representative of the ESIL network. **We also recognize the following limitations:**

1. We did not get a 100% response rate for any of the network surveys thus the data were not from of *all* the ESIL network members.
2. In Year 1, we chose to bound the network using the ESIL Innovation Summit as our sample. In subsequent years of data collection, the network boundary to include participants who attended at least one ESIL event (defined as ESIL members). We interpret the social network data with this in mind, that the Year 1 connections represent a percentage of ESIL members who attended the Summit and that Years 2 and 3 represent only ESIL members across a variety of events.
3. We changed our survey response options to include various types of collaboration that would fall under professional and interpersonal communication. In the analysis, we merged those two categories to fall under interpersonal communication. Thus, we are not able to directly compare these map dimensions from Year 1 to Year 3.
4. We chose to force symmetry on the connections between nodes in our analysis, which limits our ability to interpret the directionality of the collaborations identified in the network data.

Given these considerations, we have increased the frequency of network data collection to two times a year. We have kept ESIL as a potential organization for collaboration in the network surveys for consistency. We will continue to use average degree centrality for comparisons across ESIL network years for both the network dimensions by role and collaboration type.

Conclusions

The social network analysis characterizes the connections among people and organizations within the ESIL network and allows us to evaluate growth from year to year using the SNA metrics. In particular, social network analysis can help identify how the population of people and organizations within ESIL changes over time, and how collaborations among people and organizations develop. The network analysis highlights the strength of the network in terms of its participants from EDS-specific roles and research collaborations. It also highlights a small, but well-connected group of people who identify as advocates for or from groups underrepresented in EDS. The presence of this dimension within the network likely represents intentional recruitment and relationship building by the ESIL leadership to broaden participation in EDS through ESIL. The results of the network analysis identify opportunities for growth in the ESIL network in order to achieve the goal of “enabling an inclusive community of practice to leverage the wealth of environmental data for challenges in the environmental sciences” such as recruiting participation from members in roles that are not EDS-specific and building connections among different member groups such as ESIL’s student members.

References

Borgatti, Stephen P., Martin G. Everett, and Jeffrey C. Johnson. *Analyzing social networks*. Sage, 2018.

Appendix A: Network Survey Questions

Please consider the following definition of Environmental Data Science when answering the questions in this survey: We define EDS broadly to include any work where big data is used to drive discovery, solutions and science to understand our environment. It is highly transdisciplinary, including aspects of the natural and social sciences (that explore the environment and human interactions) and data sciences.

Please provide your first name

Please provide your last name

Please provide your email address

Please indicate which best describes your role in the broad field of Environmental Data Science (EDS). Select all that apply.

- People working in Environmental, Biological, Social Science field (1)
- People working in Computational and/or Data Science field (13)
- Data provider (2)
- (Data science) Educator (3)
- Application partner (4)
- Industry representative (5)
- Synthesis center member (7)
- Artificial Intelligence, Machine Learning and Analytics professional (8)
- Advocate for underrepresented communities, including Tribal nations (9)
- Member of (underrepresented) community, including Tribal nations (10)
- Community engagement and/or Outreach professional (14)
- Student (11)
- Other. Please describe. (12) _____

Which of the following ESIL activities have you participated in? Select all that apply.

- Innovation Summit (1)
- Hackathon or CodeFest (2)
- Working Group (3)
- AI Skills training (4)
- Cyberinfrastructure training (5)
- Cyverse Discovery Environment Training (6)
- Cloud-based computing workstations training (7)
- R & Python bilingualism training (8)
- Environmental Science and Data Cubes training (9)
- Cultural Intelligence training (10)
- Other _____(11)
- I have not participated in any ESIL activities (12)

Connections

The next section asks you to identify your connections within the work that you do around Environmental Data Science (EDS). Please include **all** of your connections, not just the ones that may be attending the ESIL summit.

We are interested in two types of connections: Personal and Organizational connections.

Personal Connections - With whom do you work on EDS projects?

Organizational Connections - Which organizations do you work with on EDS projects?

Personal Connections Questions

Display This Question:

If Connections The next section asks you to identify your connections within the work that you do ar... Is Displayed

Q8 If you are a returning survey respondent, use your invitation email to reference the names of people that you identified in the previous network survey. You may choose to keep your connections as is, revise your connections, or name additional connections with whom you are working on EDS projects.

If you are taking the survey for the first time, follow the instruction below.

Please type the full name (first and last) of the personal connections with whom you currently work on EDS projects (if any) in the text boxes provided.. As you begin typing in the box, you can select from dropdown options* or type in your connection's full name to have it recorded.

**Dropdown options are names of people who have attended ESIL events and named collaborators, but are not comprehensive of the larger EDS community.*

Please add your main EDS connections, these could be only a few or many. You are **not** required to fill all of the textboxes provided. Up to 20 textboxes have been provided.

If you have worked with ESIL members, but cannot remember the full names of people you have worked with, you can view an ESIL member list by [clicking here](#).

##[Question format for EDS-specific role]

Display This Question:

If Connections The next section asks you to identify your connections within the work that you do ar... Is Displayed

Q9 Personal connection #1:

##[Note: Questions repeat for connections up to #20]

Display This Question:

If Personal connection #1: Text Response Is Not Empty

Q30 Please indicate the nature of your collaboration with **[name of personal connection]** (Select all that apply.)*

- Ongoing research (1)
- Grant proposals for future research (2)
- Co-author on papers (3)
- Collaboration on data products (4)
- Collaboration on code or software tools (9)
- Collaboration on educational materials (5)
- Preliminary discussions (6)
- Learning (7)
- Participate with/in presentations, panels, programs and/or communities of practice (10)
- Communicate with as leader/member of the same professional organization/working group (11)
- Mentor, advisor/advisee, and/or host institution relationship (12)
- Co-worker, employer or other work relationship (13)
- Other (please explain) (8) _____

##[Note: Questions repeat for connections up to #20]

##[Question format for non-EDS-specific role]

Start of Block: SNA Personal Connections - General role

Display This Question:

If Please indicate which best describes your role in the broad field of Environmental Data Science (... = Advocate for underrepresented communities, including Tribal nations

Or Please indicate which best describes your role in the broad field of Environmental Data Science (... = Member of (underrepresented) community, including Tribal nations

Or Please indicate which best describes your role in the broad field of Environmental Data Science (... = Student

Or Please indicate which best describes your role in the broad field of Environmental Data Science (... = Other. Please describe.

And If

Connections The next section asks you to identify your connections within the work that you do ar... Is Displayed

Display This Question:

If Connections The next section asks you to identify your connections within the Environmental Data... Is Displayed

Q121 If you are a survey returning respondent, use your invitation email to reference the names of people that you identified in the network survey from last year. You may choose to keep your connections as is, revise your connections, or name additional connections with whom you are working on EDS projects.

If you are taking the survey for the first time, follow the instruction below.

Please indicate the **people** with whom you currently work with on EDS projects (if any). Type the first and last name into the text boxes provided, and the nature of your collaboration. Please add your main EDS connections, these could be only a few or many. You are **not** required to fill all of the textboxes provided. Up to 20 textboxes have been provided.

If you have worked with ESIL members, but cannot remember the full names of people you have worked with, you can view a reference list of the people involved with ESIL by [clicking here](#).

	First and Last Name(s) (1)	Nature of Collaboration (4)
Personal Connection #1 (1)		
Personal Connection #2 (2)		
Personal Connection #3 (3)		
Personal Connection #4 (4)		
Personal Connection #5 (5)		
Personal Connection #6 (6)		
Personal Connection #7 (7)		
Personal Connection #8 (8)		

##[Note: Table rows repeat for connections up to #20]

Organizational Connections

##Both EDS-specific roles and non-EDS-specific roles receive this question format

Use your invitation email to reference the names of organizations that you identified in the network survey from last year. You may choose to keep your connections as is, revise your connections, or name additional connections with whom you are working on EDS projects.

If you are taking the survey for the first time, follow the instruction below.

Please type the **organizations** with whom you currently work with on Environmental Data Science (EDS) projects (if any) in the textboxes provided. When you begin typing in the box, you can select from the dropdown options* or type in your connection's name to have it recorded.

**Dropdown options are names of people who have attended ESIL events and named collaborators, but are not comprehensive of the larger EDS community.*

Please add your main EDS organizational connections, these could be only a few or many. You are **not** required to fill all of the textboxes provided. Up to 20 textboxes have been provided.

Organizations can include research centers, institutes, universities or academic institutions, networks, private sector partners, nonprofits or other organizations. You can view a reference list of the organizations involved with ESIL by [clicking here](#).

Q128 Organization #1:

Q129 Organization #2:

Q130 Organization #3:

Q131 Organization #4:

Q132 Organization #5:

##[Note: Questions repeat for connections up to #20]

Display This Question:

*If Connections The next section asks you to identify your connections within the work that you do ar... Is Displayed
And Organization #1: Text Response Is Not Empty*

##[Question format for EDS-specific role]

Q149 Please indicate the nature of your collaboration with [organization name] (Select all that apply.)*

- Ongoing research (1)
- Grant proposals for future research (2)
- Co-author on papers (3)
- Collaboration on data products (4)
- Collaboration on code or software tools (9)
- Collaboration on educational materials (5)
- Preliminary discussions (6)
- Learning (7)
- Participate with/in presentations, panels, programs and/or communities of practice (10)
- Communicate with as leader/member of the same professional organization/working group (11)
- Mentor, advisor/advisee, and/or host institution relationship (12)
- Co-worker, employer or other work relationship (13)
- Other (please explain) (8) _____

##[Note: Questions repeat for connections up to #20]

Display This Question:

If Connections The next section asks you to identify your connections within the Environmental Data... Is Displayed
And Organization #1: Text Response Is Not Empty

##[Question format for non-EDS-specific role]

Q169 Please indicate the nature of your collaboration with [organization name]

[Note: Questions repeat for connections up to #20]

Q13 Are there people and/or organizations that you currently work with on EDS projects that are not listed here? Please provide the names, organizational affiliations, and the nature of your collaboration.

Appendix B: Lists of Organizations and People

Organization Name	ID#
AAG (American Association of Geographers)	431
AGU (American Geophysical Union)	432
AI for Conservation Slack Community	433
AIHEC (American Indian Higher Education Consortium)	434
Allen Institute for AI	435
Amazon Environmental Research Institute	436
AmeriFlux	437
Arctic Data Center	438
Arizona State University	439
Atlas of Living Australia	440
Australian Research Data Commons	441
Axiom Data Science	442
Battelle	443
Baylor University	444
BEDE Network	445
Biocultural Diversity Lab at Colorado State University	446
Biodiversity Collections Network	447
Boise State University	448
Boston University	449
Bren School of Environmental Science and Management	450
CALeDNA	451
Chicago Botanic Garden	452
CIRES (Cooperative Institute for Research in Environmental Sciences)	453
Clean Water 4 All Coalition	454
Clemson University	455
Climate Change AI	456
Climate Informatics	457
CODATA	458
College of the Muscogee Nation	459
Colorado State University	460
Cornell Lab Of Ornithology	461
County Government of Nyamira	462
Critical Zone Network	463
CUAHSI (Consortium of Universities for the Advancement of Hydrologic Science)	464
CV4Ecology	465
CyVerse	466
CZNet	467
Deloitte	468

Delta Science Program	469
Denver Botanic Gardens	470
Drexel University	471
Dynamic Water Critical Zone	472
Earth Lab	473
Ecological Forecasting Initiative	474
Ecological Society of America (ESA)	475
EDSIN (Environmental Data Science Inclusion Network)	476
Environment and Climate Change Canada	477
Environmental Data Initiative	478
Environmental Data Science journal	479
Environmental Defense Fund (EDF)	480
Environmental Policy Innovation Center	481
EREN (Ecological Research as Education Network)	482
eScience Institute	483
ESIIL (Environmental Data Science Innovation & Inclusion Lab)	484
ESIP (Earth Science Information Partners)	485
Florida Department of Health	486
Florida Medical Entomology Laboratory	487
Florida Museum	488
GEO BON	489
GEO Indigenous Alliance	490
German Aerospace Center - DLR	491
Getches-Wilkinson Center for Natural Resources, Energy, and the Environment	492
GGBN (Global Genome Biodiversity Network)	493
Google	494
Great Lakes Bioenergy Research Center	495
Harvard University	496
Haskell Indian Nations University	497
Haskell Indian Nations University - Sensing the Earth	498
Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research - UFZ	499
Holden Arboretum	500
ICAR-National Rice Research Institute, India	501
iDigBio	502
iDiv (German Centre for Integrative Biodiversity Research)	503
IIASA	504
Indian Council of Agricultural Research	505
Indigenous Peoples Climate Change Working Group	506
Insectarium of Montreal	507
INSTAAR (Institute of Arctic and Alpine Research)	508
Institute of Meteorology and Climate Research (IMK)- KIT	509

James Cook University	510
Kansas University	511
Keweenaw Bay Ojibwa College	512
Lakota Atlas	513
Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory	514
Livelihoods Knowledge Exchange Network	515
Long Term Agroecosystem Research Network	516
Los Alamos National Laboratory	517
Louisiana State Water Chemistry Department	518
ILTER (Long Term Ecological Research Network)	519
Marquette University	520
Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT)	521
MEFA (Macrosystems Ecology For All) Research Coordination Network	522
Metropolitan State University of Denver	523
Michigan State University	524
Microsoft Corporation	525
MIDAS	526
NASA	527
NASA Earth Science Data Systems	528
NASA Goddard Space Flight Center	529
NASA Harvest	530
NASA JPL	531
National Center for Disease Control Georgia	532
National Computational Infrastructure (NCI - Australia)	533
National Interagency Fire Center	534
National Phenology Network	535
National Wildfire Coordinating Group	536
Native BioData Consortium	537
NTU (Navajo Technical University)	538
NCAR (National Center for Atmospheric Research)	539
NCASC (National Climate Adaptation Science Center)	540
NCEAS (National Center for Ecological Analysis and Synthesis)	541
NCEP	542
NEON (National Ecological Observatory Network)	543
Network for Integrated Agricultural Resilience Research	544
NOAA (National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration)	545
NOAA Climate & Global Change Postdoctoral Fellowship	546
NOAA GSL (Global Systems Laboratory)	547
NOAA NCAS-M (Cooperative Science Center in Atmospheric Sciences and Meteorology)	548
NOAA NCEI (National Centers for Environmental Information)	549
North Carolina Institute for Climate Studies	550

Northern Arizona University	551
Northern Illinois University	552
Northern Jaguar Project	553
Northwestern University	554
NSF (National Science Foundation)	555
Ocean Vision AI	556
Oglala Lakota College	557
Ohio State University	558
Open Knowledge Nepal	559
Oregon State University	560
Pacific Northwest National Laboratory	561
Penn State University	562
PhenoCam Network	563
Planet Labs	564
Polar Geospatial Center	565
Princeton University	566
Project Red Bus	567
Purdue University	568
pyOpenSci	569
Pyrologix LLC/Vibrant Planet	570
Queensland University of Technology	571
RDA	572
Rio de Janeiro Botanical Garden	573
RISCC	574
ROpenSci	575
Rosebud Sioux Tribe	576
Rosebud Sioux Tribe - Sicangu Climate Center	577
Rutgers University	578
Salish Kootenai College	579
San Diego State University	580
SESYNC (National Socio-Environmental Synthesis Center)	581
SIKU	582
SIPI	583
Smithsonian National Museum of Natural History	584
Southern California Coastal Water Research Project	585
Southwestern Indian Polytechnic Institute	586
Stony Brook University	587
TCUs	588
Technical University of Munich	589
Tel Aviv University	590
TERN Australia (Terrestrial Ecosystem Research Network)	591

Texas A&M University	592
Texas Parks and Wildlife	593
The Carpentries	594
The Living Data Project	595
The Nature Conservancy	596
The Public Knowledge Workshop (NGO, IL)	597
TU Dresden	598
UC Berkeley Data Science & Environment	599
UCAR (University Corporation for Atmospheric Research)	600
UCSB Master of Environmental Data Science (MEDS)	601
UF Florida Institute of Built Environmental Resilience	602
Unidata (UCAR Community Programs)	603
United Tribes Technical College	604
University of Adelaide	605
University of Alabama	606
University of Arizona	607
University of California Berkeley	608
University of California Davis	609
University of California Irvine	610
University of California Los Angeles	611
University of California Merced	612
University of California Santa Barbara	613
University of California Santa Cruz	614
University of Colorado Boulder (CU Boulder)	615
University of Florida	616
University of Guam	617
University of Maine	618
University of Maryland	619
University of Massachusetts Amherst	620
University of Miami	621
University of Michigan	622
University of Montana	623
University of New Mexico	624
University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill	625
University of Oregon	626
University of Oslo	627
University of Puerto Rico	628
University of Queensland	629
University of Rhode Island	630
University of South Carolina	631
University of Sydney	632

University of Texas at El Paso	633
University of Washington	634
University of Wisconsin-Madison	635
US National Park Service	636
USA-NPN (National Phenology Network)	637
USDA-ARS (Agricultural Research Service)	638
USDA (Beltsville, Maryland, USA)	639
USDA (United States Department of Agriculture)	640
USFS (United States Forest Service)	641
USFS Rocky Mountain Research Station	642
USFWS (United States Fish and Wildlife Service)	643
USGS (United States Geological Survey)	644
USGS CASC (Climate Adaptation Science Centers)	645
USGS GBIF-US (Global Biodiversity Information Facility)	646
USGS OBIS-USA (Ocean Biodiversity Information System)	647
USGS Powell Center	648
Water & Tribes Initiative	649
White House Office for Science and Technology Policy (OSTP)	650
Wildlife Insights	651
Woods Hole Oceanographic Institute	652
Woodwell Climate Research Center	653
University of Bonn	2001
VITO	2002
BC3	2003
University of Porto	2004
Federal University of Alfenas	2005
Czech University of Life Sciences	2006
IAVS Working Group for Ecoinformatics (International Association for Vegetation Science)	2007
ESA Vegetation Classification Panel (Ecological Society of America)	2008
FGDC Subcommittee on Vegetation Classification (U.S. Federal Geographic Data Committee)	2009
NatureServe Panel for National Vegetation Classification	2010
sPlot (Global Vegetation Plot Database Working Group, German Centre for Integrative Biodiversity Research)	2011
Carolina Vegetation Survey	2012
GIVD (Global Index of Vegetation Plot Databases)	2013
TNRS (Taxonomic Name Resolution Service)	2014
BIEN (Botanical Information and Ecology Network)	2015
Resurvey Europe	2016
American Society of Microbiology (ASM)	2017
Master of Environmental Data Science program (Bren)	2018
R-Ladies	2019
Dartmouth College	2020

DRYAD	2021
Environmental Data Initiative	2022
Open Environmental Data Project	2023
Area de Conservación Guanacaste	2024
University of Vermont	2025
Hacking Limnology	2026
University of Wyoming	2027
Cary Institute of Ecosystem Studies	2028
Global Lake Ecological Observatory Network	2029
Earth Science Women's Network	2030
South Dakota State University	2031
University of North Dakota	2032
ESA SEEDS	2033
DataONE	2034
AI Center for Societal Decision Making	2035
Block Power	2036
Bezos Earth Foundation	2037
SinBiose	2038
South Florida Water Management District	2039
Imageomic	2040
Radnor to River	2041
Affiliated Tribes of Northwest Indians	2042
North Carolina State University	2043
Biodiversity Information Standards, Taxonomic Data Working Group (TDWG)	2044

ESIL members represented in the network maps (n=316)

Aarti Singh	Amely Bauer	Ben Weinstein	Catherine Jarnevich	Courtney Scarborough	Elisa Girola
Abby Benson	Amy De Castro	Benjamin Zuckerberg	Catherine O'Reilly	Crystal Kolden	Elisha Yellow Thunder
Abigail Toretsky	Amy Goldman	Beryl Morris	Cathleen Torres Parisian	Daijiang Li	Elizabeth Hiroyasu
Abigail Ward	Amy McGovern	Bob Newman	Cayelan Carey	Dan Gavin	Elizabeth Joyner
Abu Namzaideh	Amy Quarkume	Bob Rabin	Cesar Terror	Dan Wildcat	Elizabeth LaRue
Adam Mahood	Ana M. Tarano	Bonnie Meinke	Chandra Earl	Dana Chadwick	Elizabeth von Holle
Adeline Kelly	Ananya Roy	Brett Melbourne	Charles Jason Tinant	Dana Gehring	Ellen Bledsoe
Adrienne Marshall	Andrea Anteau	Brian Gerber	Charlie Catlett	Daphne LaDue	Ellen Denny
Al Kuslikis	Andrea Garcia	Brian Knight	Charuleka Varadharajan	Daphne Virlar-Knight	Elsa Culler
Alex Barth	Andrew Elmore	Brian Yandell	Chelsea Cook	Darian Sorenson	Emiley Eloe-Fadros
Alex Rose	Andrew Richardson	Bridget Hass	Chelsea Nagy	Dave Calkin	Emily Biggane
Alexa Azure	Aneesh Subramanian	Caitlin White	Chris Beirne	Dave Jones	Emily Harbo
Alexandra Phillips	Angela Strecker	Cameron Egan	Chris Bretherton	David Parr	Emily Ward
Alexey Voinov	Angela Zhu	Cami Griffith	Chris Guiterman	Deb Agarwal	Eric Kihn
Alicia Foxx	Ankur Desai	Camila Vargas-Poulsen	Chris Hakkenberg	Debora Pignatari Drucker	Eric Parrish
Alisa Coffin	Ann Marie Chischilly	Caren Scott	Chris Ray	Dellena Bloom	Eric Sokol
Alison Post	Anna Boser	Carl Boettiger	Chris Rezendes	Dennis Dye	Erick Verleye
Allan Craig	Anne Gold	Carl Norlen	Chris Slocum	Di Yang	Erin Belval
Allison Horst	Antonio Mauro Saraiva	Carlos A. Botero	Christina Grozinger	Diane Srivastava	Erin Polka
Allison Myers-Pigg	Ariel Simons	Carlos Aguilar	Christine Laney	Diego Brizuela	Erin Robinson
Alycia Crall	Ashok Srinivasan	Carmen Galaz Garcia	Chuck Davis	Douglas Mbura	Esther Rolf
Alyssa Rosemartin	Assaf Anyamba	Carmina Gutierrez	Cibele Amaral	Dylan Simpson	Ethan White
Amanda Carr	Bailey Murphy	Carol Wessman	Claire Lunch	Easton White	Eva Kinnebrew
Amanda Hughes	Bala Chaudhary	Carolina Barbosa	Claire Monteleoni	Ed Hackett	Evan Fricke
Amanda Richey	Barbara Bomfim	Carrie Diaz Eaton	Clinton Francis	Edwin Skidmore	Felipe Montealegre
Amanda S. Hering	Barbara M. Thiers	Carrie Wall	Cole Kellerer	Eimear M Nic Lughadha	Feng Gao
Amber Finley	Ben Baiser	Carsten Meyer	Corey Smith	EJ Rainville	Firouzeh Taghikhah
Amber Laundreaux	Ben Halpern	Casey Jenson	Corinna Gries	Elie Alhajjar	Foster Sawyer
Amber Runyon	Ben Poulter	Cassie Buhler			
		Catherine Hulshof			

Francisco J. Guerrero	Isaac Shepard	Jessica Matthews	Julie Maldonado	Kelly Aho	Liz Amador
Frannie Monasterio	Isabella Olesky	Jessica Weidenfeld	Julie Padilla	Kelly Caylor	Liz LaRue
Gabriel Abreu-Vigil	Jack Dangermond	Jhon Goes In Center	Julie Steward-Lowndes	Kelly Easterday	Liz Neeley
Gabriel Kamener	Jada Daniels	James Marquis	Julien Brun	Kendi Davies	Lizabeth Amador
Garrett Knowlton	James Marquis	Jie Hu	Justina White Eyes	Kerry Cawse-Nicholson	Lola Fatoyinbo
Gary McIntyre	James Randererson	Jim Sanovia	Kabir Peay	Kerstin Lehnert	Lucas Harris
Gavin Simpson	James Rattling Leaf	Jingyi Huang	Kai Zhu	Khum Thapa-Magar	Luciana Alves
Gerardo Armendariz	James Stegen	Jinsu Elhance	Kali Dale	Kimberly Cook	Mansi Shah
Grant Foster	Jamie Montgomery	Joan Damerow	Karen Bailey	Kimberly Thompson	Marcia Macedo
Gregory Maurer	Jared Rennie	Joe Miller	Karen C. Short	Kirk Klausmeyer	Margaret Palmer
Guthrie Ducheneaux	Jason Stockwell	Joe Scott	Karen Cozzetto	Kristina Riemer	Marie Faust
Halina Do-Linh	Jason Tinant	Johannes Uhl	Karen Short	Krystal Tsosie	Marina Kogan
Hamidreza Norouzi	Jason West	John Abatzoglu	Karena Yan	Kshitiz Khanal	Marina Wolowski
Hande Benson	Jean Paul Metzger	John Fasullo	Kari Segraves	Kylie Rezendes	Mark Finney
Hannah Haynie	Jeanette Clark	John Musinsky	Karin Riley	Kyra Clark-Wolf	Markelle Kelly
Hannah Zonneville	Jeannine Cavender-Bares	John Parker	Karthik Balaguru	Lala Kounta	Martha Anderson
Hao Ye	Jeff Atkins	John Platt	Karyn Tabor	Lara Kueppers	Martha Downs
Hari Prasanna Das	Jeff Weber	John Sawyer	Kassandra Lassagne	Laura Dee	Martin Keller
Haruko Wainwright	Jeffery Oliver	John Zobitz	Kat Le	Laurel Larsen	Marty Downs
Helen Sofaer	Jeffrey Sward	Jonathan Chase	Kate Thibault	Leandro Freitas	Maruthi Sridhar Balaji Bhaskar
Henry Harwood	Jennifer Balch	Jonathan Pauli	Katharine Suding	Legand Burge	Matt Kane
Hilary Brumberg	Jennifer Kovacs	Jonathan Sanderman	Kathe Todd-Brown	Leonard Boussioux	Matt Rossi
Hilary Dugan	Jennifer Powers	Jonathan Walter	Katherine Halama	Lesley Wyborn	Matthew Jones
Hillary Hull	Jens-Christian Svenning	Joni Tobacco	Katherine Siegel	Levi Simons	Matthew Pearce
Hsun-Yi Hsieh	Jose Augusto Salim	Jose Roberto Motta Garcia	Kathleen Prudic	Li Kui	Matthew Ross
Ian Breckheimer	Jose Roberto Motta Garcia	Joseph Burant	Kathryn McConnell	Lihui Lydia Zhang	Max Cook
Ian Pearse	Joseph Yracheta	Joseph Yracheta	Katie Jones	Lillian Aoki	Maxwell Cook
	Jessica Burnett	Juan Carlos Alvarez Yepiz	Kayna Agostini	Lilly Jones	Megan Cattau
	Jessica Logan	Julia Kelliher	Keith Krause	Lindsay Campbell	Megan Littrell
			Kel Markert	Lise St Denis	Megan Mills-Novoa

Melanie Kammerer	Natty Rindlaub	Phoebe Zarnetske	Samantha Csik	Susan Sullivan	Valentin Stefan
Melissa Lucash	Naupaka Zimmerman	Rachel King	Sandy Sum	Sven Bohms	Valerio Pillar
Mercedes Bustamante	Nayan Mallick	Rachel Lieber	Sara Beery	Sydne Record	Van Butsic
Michael Binford	Nayani Ilangakoon	Rachel Meyer	Sara Paull	Tad Dallas	Veronica Southerland
Michael Gavin	Nick Haddad	Randy Swaty	Sarah Collins	Tait Weicht	Virginia Iglesias
Michael Koontz	Nick Lyon	Raphael Apeaning	Sarah Cuprewich	Talitha Washington	Wai Ho Chak
Michael Meyer	Nico Franz	Raphel Mazor	Sarah Elmendorf	Tamma Carleton	Werner Rammer
Michael Packard	Nicolas Betancourt	Ray Marszalek	Sarah Stone	Tanya Berger-Wolfe	Will Wieder
Michael Wurm	Nicole Hemming-Schroeder	Rebecca Batchelor	Saumya Sinha	Tawa Ducheneaux	Xingchao Chen
Michele Cosi	Nidhin Harilal	Reginald Blake	Scott Jasechko	TC Chkraborty	Xingyuan Chen
Michelle Dovil	Nirav Merchant	Renee F. Brown	Scotty Strachan	Ted Haberman	Yang Li
Mike Dietze	Nneamaka Uba	Rob Guralnick	Sen Chiao	Terri Adams	Yang Zhang
Mike Koontz	Nsalambi Nkongolo	Rob Redmon	Shadya Sanders	Theresa Crimmins	Yasmin Tavares
Mike San Clements	Olanrewaju Johnson	Robert Hensley	Shana Sundstrum	Thomas Martin	Yuhan Rao
Miles Moore	Oludunsin Arodudu	Robert Newman	Shashi Konduri	Thomas Michael Lewinsohn	Yun Qian
Millie Chapman	Otis Brown	Robert Peet	Shelby Weis	Thomas Stark	Yun Yang
Ming Posa	Paola Barajas	Robin Omalley	Siddeswara Guru	Tiffany Marie Knight	Zhe Feng
Mirko Karan	Park Williams	Rodrigo Leite	Sigal Kaplan	Tim Whiteaker	Zoe Pollard
Monica Turner	Patrick Freeland	Ronan Foley	Simon Cox	Timberley Roane	
Morgan Ernest	Patrisse Vasek	Ronit Purian	Sparkle Malone	Timon Keller	
Mostafa Javadian	Paul Choi	Roshelle Pederson	Spencer Clark	Tong Liu	
Mykhailo Rudko	Paul Taillie	Rosie Patrick	Stace Beaulieu	Tong Qiu	
Nancy Emery	Paula Mabee	Ruby L. Leung	Stefan Leyk	Tristan Goulden	
Natalie Mastin	Peter Isaac	Rud Platt	Stevan Earl	Ty Tuff	
Natalie Meyers	Phil Townsend	Rupert Seidl	Steve Goldstein	Tyler McIntosh	
Natalie Robinson	Philimon Two Eagle	Ruth Oliver	Steven Allison	Tyson Swetnam	
Nathan A. Quarderer	Philip Higuera	Ruth Plenty Sweetgrass-She Kills	Steven Miller	Tzahi Y. Cath	
Nathan Emery	Philip Robertson	Sally Wang	Steven Nerem	Vaasuki Marupaka	
Nathan Korinek			Summer Dupree		
Nathan Quarderer			Susan Cook-Patton		